

Answers for *Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors*

General

Topic

What is the main research question of the project?

What is the relation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors?

Please give some keywords describing the research question.

- Correlation Experiment
- LA City
- LA Crimes
- Los Angeles
- Data Science
- Crimes and Museums
- Data Experiment
- Data Correlation

Research field

Which research field(s) does this project belong to?

- Humanities and Social Sciences / Social Sciences

Which persons or institutions are responsible for the project coordination?

- Technische Universität Wien

Project schedule

When does the project start?

April 1, 2019

When does the project end?

April 20, 2019

Project coordination

Which persons or institutions are responsible for the project coordination?

- Technische Universität Wien

Other requirements I

Are there requirements regarding the data management from other parties (e.g. the scholarly/scientific community)?

No

Content classification

What kind of dataset is it?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: LA crimes dataset is owned by Los Angeles Police Department, and it had 26 data attributes, the most important ones were the date of occurrence, the victim information (e.g. gender, age, race) and the crime description. Adding to that, there were 1.9 Million incidents recorded in the dataset. Its format was a comma separated values “csv”, and contains only normal numbers and plain text.

LA museum visitors: LA museums visitors dataset is owned by Los Angeles Open Data, and it had 12 columns, the first one was the month in which the reading was taken in, and the other 11 columns represented the numbers of visitors for 11 different museums. This dataset also contains of a set of normal numbers and plain text in a comma separated values “csv” format.

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: This dataset contains the aggregated results of analyzing other two datasets, it contains 6 columns starting with the one indicating the reading type, then the years of which the reading was taken for. It was generated following csv format and it contains only normal numbers and plain text.

Is the dataset being created or re-used?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: Re-used

LA museum visitors: Re-used

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: Created

If re-used, who created the dataset?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: Los Angeles Police Department

LA museum visitors: Los Angeles Open Data

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors:

If re-used, under which address, PID or URL can the dataset be found?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: <https://doi.org/10.5282/dmp.LAexperiment.data>

LA museum visitors: <https://doi.org/10.5282/dmp.LAexperiment.data>

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: <https://doi.org/10.5282/dmp.LAexperiment.data>

Which individuals, groups or institutions could be interested in re-using this dataset? What are possible scenarios?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: This dataset shows all reported incidents occurred in LA from 2010, it can be useful for governmental usage in the US, and for human behaviour studies. For instance, it could be used for a study in which the government can specify how violence in some areas can be compared to other areas. It can be also used for studies about what race is more exposed to violence.

LA museum visitors: In this dataset, there are several readings for several museums in LA, so it could be very helpful to study the interest ratio in museums categories. Adding to that, it could be used as an indicator

of how art is evolving which may attract some data scientists to test the correlation of showing interest to some category of museums in a specific period of time.

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: The generated data could be used as it's for the sake of finding how the crime rate could be affected by the number of people visiting museums in a certain year. It could be interesting for local citizens or even data scientists to compare it with other aggregated data.

Is the dataset reproducible in the sense that it could be created / collected anew in case it got lost?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: yes, with little effort

LA museum visitors: yes, with little effort

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: yes, with little effort

Technical classification

When does data collection or creation start?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: Jan. 1, 2010

LA museum visitors: Jan. 1, 2014

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: Jan. 17, 2014

When does data collection or creation end?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: April 17, 2019

LA museum visitors: March 1, 2019

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: April 17, 2019

When does data cleansing / data preparation start?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: April 19, 2019

LA museum visitors: April 17, 2019

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: April 17, 2019

When does data cleansing / data preparation end?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: April 19, 2019

LA museum visitors: April 17, 2019

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: April 17, 2019

When does data analysis start?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: April 19, 2019

LA museum visitors: April 17, 2019

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: April 17, 2019

When does data analysis end?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: April 19, 2019

LA museum visitors: April 17, 2019

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: April 17, 2019

What is the actual or expected size of the dataset?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: exact size: 437 MB

LA museum visitors: exact size: 4 KB

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: exact size: 1 KB

How much data is produced per year?

LA crime data from 2010 to present:

LA museum visitors:

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors:

Which file formats are used?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: Data was provided in a CSV (Comma Separated Values) file format, which is readable by all text editors, sheet programs and programmable APIs.

LA museum visitors: Data was provided in a CSV (Comma Separated Values) file format, which is readable by all text editors, sheet programs and programmable APIs.

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: Data was provided in a CSV (Comma Separated Values) file format, which is readable by all text editors, sheet programs and programmable APIs.

Which tools, software, technologies or processes are used to generate or collect the data?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: Data is provided by Los Angeles Police Department, and they didn't publish how they collected it.

LA museum visitors: Data is provided by City of Los Angeles, and they didn't publish how they collected it.

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: I implemented a java code in order to generate this data out from other two datasets: 1- LA crime data from 2010 to present 2- LA museum visitors

Which software, processes or technologies are necessary to use the data?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: As a CSV file format, all you need is a text editor or a sheet software (e.g. Excel) or a programmable API that can read text files.

LA museum visitors: As a CSV file format, all you need is a text editor or a sheet software (e.g. Excel) or a programmable API that can read text files.

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: As a CSV file format, all you need is a text editor or a sheet software (e.g. Excel) or a programmable API that can read text files.

Is documentation about relevant software needed to use the data?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: No

LA museum visitors: No

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: No

Are different versions of the dataset created?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: No

LA museum visitors: No

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: Yes

Which versioning strategy is applied for this dataset?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: Versioning strategy was not published by the data owner.

LA museum visitors: Versioning strategy was not published by the data owner.

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: Output data could be changed if the period of study has changed by adding new readings for new years by the studies. Each version will be uploaded to Zenodo repository with a unique DOI. Adding to that, the same output data is being stored on Bitbucket git repository.

Which technology or tool is used for versioning?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: Not yet decided

LA museum visitors: Not yet decided

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: Version control system: <https://bitbucket.org/hasanalkhatib/laexperiment>

Data usage

How / for what purpose will this dataset be used during the project?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: This dataset was used to get the numbers of crimes grouped by years in the city of Los Angeles.

LA museum visitors: This dataset was used to get the numbers of museums visitors per each year in the city of Los Angeles.

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: This is the result of the project which shows the correlation between LA crimes and museums visitors.

How often will this dataset be used?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: It can be used as many times as needed by others

LA museum visitors: It can be used as many times as needed by others

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: This dataset can be used as many as possible if the studied period results are needed.

To what extent will infrastructure resources be required (e.g. CPU hours, bandwidth, storage space... etc.).

LA crime data from 2010 to present: Infrastructure resources of the usual workplace equipment are sufficient.

LA museum visitors: Infrastructure resources of the usual workplace equipment are sufficient.

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: Infrastructure resources of the usual workplace equipment are sufficient.

Are there actual or potential usage scenarios that could benefit from support by a data management or IT expert, or that even require such support?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: Yes: If the process requires generating new data, there will be a need for an expert to aggregate data.

LA museum visitors: Yes: If the process requires generating new data, there will be a need for an expert to aggregate data.

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: No

Where is the dataset stored during the project?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: Data were stored on both Zenodo repository and Bitbucket git repository.

LA museum visitors: Data were stored on both Zenodo repository and Bitbucket git repository.

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: Data were stored on both Zenodo repository and Bitbucket git repository.

Under which URL can the dataset be accessed during the project?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: https://bitbucket.org/hasanalkhatib/laexperiment_data/src/master/

LA museum visitors: https://bitbucket.org/hasanalkhatib/laexperiment_data/src/master/

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: https://bitbucket.org/hasanalkhatib/laexperiment_data/src/master/

Are there internal project guidelines for a consistent organisation of the data? If so, where they are documented?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: No

LA museum visitors: No

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: No

Is there a internal project guideline for naming the data? If so, please briefly outline the naming conventions and, if necessary, link to the documentation.

LA crime data from 2010 to present: No

LA museum visitors: No

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: No

Who is allowed to access the dataset?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: It's openly accessed for all users to share and use.

LA museum visitors: It's openly accessed for all users to share and use.

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: Data is published for public access under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

How and how often will backups of the data be created?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: The owner of data didn't mention that.

LA museum visitors: The owner of data didn't mention that.

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: For each update on the generated data there is a backup taken to Bitbucket.

Who is responsible for the backups?

LA crime data from 2010 to present:

-

LA museum visitors:

-

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors:

- Hasan Alkhatib

Which measures or provisions are in place to ensure data security (e.g. protection against unauthorized access, data recovery, transfer of sensitive data)?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: It's placed on an official website that allow only authorized users.

LA museum visitors: It's placed on an official website that allow only authorized users.

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: Data can't be changed on Zenodo from the time the DOI citation was created. For Bitbucket, only authorized users can access master branch.

Is this dataset interoperable, i.e. allowing data exchange and re-use between researchers, institutions, organisations, countries etc.?

LA crime data from 2010 to present:

- The dataset adheres to standardised formats: csv
- The dataset is usable with available (open) software applications or software applications that are established and widely used in the respective community: text editors and any sheet manipulation software
- The dataset can easily be re-combined with different datasets from different origins: because it contains plain text and normal number

LA museum visitors:

- The dataset adheres to standardised formats: csv
- The dataset is usable with available (open) software applications or software applications that are established and widely used in the respective community: text editors and any sheet manipulation software
- The dataset can easily be re-combined with different datasets from different origins: because it contains plain text and normal number

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors:

- The dataset adheres to standardised formats: csv
- The dataset is usable with available (open) software applications or software applications that are established and widely used in the respective community: text editors and any sheet manipulation software
- The dataset can easily be re-combined with different datasets from different origins: because it contains plain text and normal number

Will this dataset be published or shared?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: Yes, externally for everyone

LA museum visitors: Yes, externally for everyone

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: Yes, externally for everyone

If no, please explain why not. Please differentiate between legal and contractual reasons and voluntary restrictions.

LA crime data from 2010 to present:

LA museum visitors:

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors:

If yes, under which terms of use or license will the dataset be published or shared?

LA crime data from 2010 to present:</>

- Public domain (CC0)

LA museum visitors:</>

- Public domain (CC0)

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors:</>

- Public domain (CC0)

If there are any restrictions on the re-use of this dataset, please explain why.

LA crime data from 2010 to present: There are no restrictions on reusing dataset.

LA museum visitors: There are no restrictions on reusing dataset.

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: There are no restrictions on reusing dataset.

When will the data be published (if they are)?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: April 10, 2017

LA museum visitors: Aug. 16, 2018

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: April 20, 2019

Will the data be collaboratively used?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: No

LA museum visitors: No

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: No

Which platform / tools is / are used for collaboratively working on data and publications?

LA crime data from 2010 to present:

LA museum visitors:

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors:

How is the collaborative work on the same files organised?

LA crime data from 2010 to present:

LA museum visitors:

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors:

Which measures of quality assurance are taken for this dataset?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: A method I used for assuring the experiment was to work with a small sample file from the input data and check results. Other than that the process was going smoothly as all data attributes are primitive types.

LA museum visitors: A method I used for assuring the experiment was to work with a small sample file from the input data and check results. Other than that the process was going smoothly as all data attributes are primitive types.

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: A method I used for assuring the experiment was to work with a small sample file from the input data and check results. Other than that the process was going smoothly as all data attributes are primitive types.

Data integration

Is the integration between the re-used and newly created data ensured? If yes, by which means?

No, there is no specific integration between data.

Costs

What are the personnel costs for data management associated with the creation or acquisition of data in the project?

0.5 PM

What is the amount of non-personnel-costs for data management associated with the creation or acquisition of data in the project?

0 Euro

What are the personnel costs for data management associated with the the usage of data in the project?

0.5 PM

What is the amount of non-personnel-costs for data management associated with the usage of data in the project?

0 Euro

What are the personnel costs associated with data storage and data security in the project?

0.5 PM

What is the amount of non-personnel costs associated with the storage of the data sets during the project?

0 Euro

Metadata and referencing

Which information is necessary for other parties to understand the data (that is, to understand their collection or creation, analysis, and research results obtained on its basis) and to re-use it?

LA crime data from 2010 to present:</>

- Location
- Content
- Time

LA museum visitors:</>

- Location
- Content
- Time

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors:</>

- Location
- Content
- Creation process
- Time
- Sources

Which standards, ontologies, classifications etc. are used to describe the data and context information?

LA crime data from 2010 to present:</>

- No fixed system for the description is used

LA museum visitors:</>

- No fixed system for the description is used

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors:</>

- Discipline-specific standards, classifications etc. are used: DCMI schema metadata

Which metadata are collected automatically?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: Data owner didn't mention that.

LA museum visitors: Data owner didn't mention that.

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: Metadata weren't collected automatically.

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project-specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: No

LA museum visitors: No

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: Yes

Which metadata are collected semi-automatically?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: Data owner didn't mention that.

LA museum visitors: Data owner didn't mention that.

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: Metadata weren't collected semi-automatically.

Which metadata are collected manually?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: Data owner didn't mention that.

LA museum visitors: Data owner didn't mention that.

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: All described metadata were collected manually according to DCMI schema standard.

Are metadata and context information being checked for correctness and completeness?

LA crime data from 2010 to present:</>

- Other: N/A

LA museum visitors:</>

- Other: N/A

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors:</>

- Manual check for completeness

Who is responsible for documenting the metadata and context information and for checking if they are correct and complete?

LA crime data from 2010 to present:</>

- Data Owner

LA museum visitors:</>

- Data Owner

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors:</>

- Hasan Alkhatib

Metadata costs

What are the personnel costs associated with the the creation of metadata and context information in the project?

0.5 PM

What is the amount of non-personnel-costs associated with the creation of metadata and context information in the project?

0 Euro

What is the structure of the data? How are the individual components of the dataset related to each other? How is the dataset related to other datasets used in the project?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: This dataset was following the CSV structure, each data raw referring to a crime incident that has 26 data attribute such as the crime date and when it was reported. In order to serve the purpose of the experiment, this data was grouped by years in order to be used in the correlation dataset.

LA museum visitors: This dataset was following the CSV structure, each data raw referring to the number of museums visitors for each month, and it has 12 data attributes to show the number of visitors per each museum. In order to serve the purpose of the experiment, this data was grouped by years in order to be used in the correlation dataset.

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: This is the generated data, which follows the CSV format and has the aggregated results from the input data.

Will persistent identifiers (PIDs) be used for this data set?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: Yes

LA museum visitors: Yes

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: Yes

Which system of persistent identifiers shall be used?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: Handle / DOI

LA museum visitors: Handle / DOI

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: Handle / DOI

Which (sub-) entities / sub units should be referenced using identifiers? Which of those identifiers should be persistent and citable?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: The dataset CSV file.

LA museum visitors: The dataset CSV file.

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: The dataset CSV file.

Who is responsible for the maintenance of the PIDs and the object maintenance (i.e. who is responsible notifying the PID-Service about object relocation and the new address)?

LA crime data from 2010 to present:</>

- Researcher (Hasan Alkhatib)

LA museum visitors:</>

- Researcher (Hasan Alkhatib)

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors:</>

- Researcher (Hasan Alkhatib)

PIDs costs

What are the personnel costs associated with of persistent identifiers in the project?

0.5 PM

What is the amount of non-personnel-costs associated with persistent identifiers in the project?

0 Euro

Legal and ethics

General legal issues

Does the legal situation of different countries have to be considered?

No

Does this dataset contain personal data?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: No

LA museum visitors: No

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: No

Does this dataset contain sensitive data other than personal data?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: No

LA museum visitors: No

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: No

If yes, please describe the non-personal sensitive data used in the project.

LA crime data from 2010 to present: N/A

LA museum visitors: N/A

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: N/A

Does the funder have rules or recommendations for data management? If yes, please briefly outline them and refer to more detailed sources of information if necessary. Please also indicate, if the rules / guidelines are mandatory or optional.

LA crime data from 2010 to present: N/A

LA museum visitors: N/A

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: N/A

Official approval

Has the project been approved by a research ethics committee?

No, a review is not necessary, because: All data was anonymized

Is a statutory approval / permit needed for the research?

No

If yes, which permit?

If yes, which is the responsible agency?

Is a data access committee needed to handle access requests to the published data of the project?

No

Intellectual property rights I

Does the project use and/or produce data that is protected by intellectual or industrial property rights?

No

Storage and long-term preservation

Selection

What are the criteria / rules for the selection of the data to be archived (after the end of the project)?

All input data that were used to generate data in this experiment were archived on Zenodo repository. And the output data was archived too. In general, any data that would affect the output were archived and the same goes to data affect the results.

Who selects the data to be archived?

- Researcher (Hasan Alkhatib)

Does this dataset have to preserved for the long-term?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: Yes

LA museum visitors: Yes

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: Yes

What are the reasons this dataset has to be preserved for the long-term?

LA crime data from 2010 to present:</>

- Used in a publication / proof of good scientific practice
- Re-use in subsequent projects or by others
- Documentation, because it is relevant to society
- Self-commitment

LA museum visitors:</>

- Used in a publication / proof of good scientific practice
- Re-use in subsequent projects or by others
- Documentation, because it is relevant to society
- Self-commitment

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors:</>

- Used in a publication / proof of good scientific practice
- Re-use in subsequent projects or by others
- Documentation, because it is relevant to society
- Self-commitment

How long will the data be stored?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: No limits

LA museum visitors: No limits

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: No limits

How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable.

LA crime data from 2010 to present: No limits

LA museum visitors: No limits

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: No limits

Where will the data (including metadata, documentation and, if applicable, relevant code) be stored or archived after the end of the project?

LA crime data from 2010 to present:</>

- Generic data center: CERN Data Center

LA museum visitors:</>

- Generic data center: CERN Data Center

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors:</>

- Generic data center: CERN Data Center

Is the repository or data centre chosen certified (e.g. Data Seal of Approval, nestor Seal or ISO 16363)? (If the dataset is archived at several places, you may answer this question with yes, if this applies to at least one of these.)

LA crime data from 2010 to present: Yes

LA museum visitors: Yes

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: Yes

Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: No

LA museum visitors: No

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: No

Shall there be an embargo period before the data are made available?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: No, it has to be available after publishing it on Zenodo which will store it on CERN Data Center.

LA museum visitors: No, it has to be available after publishing it on Zenodo which will store it on CERN Data Center.

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: No, it has to be available after publishing it on Zenodo which will store it on CERN Data Center.

How will the identity of the person accessing the data will be ascertained?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: By using individual user account authentication on Zenodo or Bitbucket.

LA museum visitors: By using individual user account authentication on Zenodo or Bitbucket.

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: By using individual user account authentication on Zenodo or Bitbucket.

By when will the data be archived?

LA crime data from 2010 to present: April 19, 2019

LA museum visitors: April 19, 2019

Correlation between LA Crimes and Museum Visitors: April 17, 2019

Long-term preservation costs

What are the personnel costs associated with long-term preservation for the project?

0.5 PM

How will the datamanagement costs of the project be covered?

There is no costs regarding this data management project.

What is the amount of non-personnel-costs regarding long-term preservation for the project?

0 Euro